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Low Work Intensity in the Italian Regions in the Period 2004-2021

Between 2004 and 2021 it decreased on average by 0.04%

Istat calculates the low work intensity in the Italian regions. The variable is defined as the percentage of people living in families for which the ratio between the total number of months worked by family members during the income reference year and the total number of months theoretically available for work activities is lower at 0.20. For the purposes of calculating this ratio, family members aged between 18 and 59 are considered, excluding students in the age range between 18 and 24. Families composed only of minors, students under the age of 25 and people aged 60 or over are not considered in the calculation of the indicator. The data refers to the period between 2004 and 2021 for the Italian regions and macro-regions.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of low work intensity in 2021. Campania is in first place by value of low work intensity in 2021 with an amount of 29.6, followed by Sicily with 22.9 and Sardinia with a value of 18.4 units. In the middle of the table are Liguria with a value of 10.6 units, followed by Basilicata with an amount of 9.8 and Friuli Venezia Giulia with an amount of 8.4. Trentino Alto Adige closes the ranking with an amount of 5.4, followed by Lombardy with a value of 5.3 units and Emilia Romagna with a value of 3.9 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by percentage change in low work intensity between 2004 and 2021. Molise is in first place for the value of the percentage change in low work intensity with an amount of 81.25% corresponding to a change from an amount of 8.00 units up to a value of 14.5 units. Abruzzo follows with a variation equal to +65.00% corresponding to an increase from 8 units in 2004 up to 13.2 units in 2021 or equal to an amount of 5.2 units. In third place is Campania with a variation in low work intensity from an amount of 21.1 units in 2004 up to a value of 29.6 units in 2021 or equal to a variation of 40.28%. In the middle of the table are the Marche with a variation equal to -2.50% corresponding to a variation from 8 units in 2004 up to 7.8 units in 2021. Basilicata follows with a variation equal to -11.71% corresponding to a decrease from an amount of 11.1 units in 2004 to 9.8 units in 2021 or -1.3 units. In tenth place is Lazio with a variation from an amount of 13.1 units up to 11.4 units or equal to a variation of -12.98%. Umbria closes the ranking with a variation of -31.31% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 9.9 in 2004 to 6.8 in 2021 or equal to -3.1 units. Emilia Romagna follows with a variation equal to an amount of -40.00% equal to a variation from 6.5 units in 2004 up to an amount of 3.9 units. Calabria closes the ranking with a variation of -40.70%, equal to a reduction from an amount of 19.90 units in 2004 to 11.8 in 2021. Between 2004 and 2021 the value of low work intensity in the Italian regions it remained more or less constant with a slight reduction from an amount of 11.09 units to a value of 11.05 units.

The low work intensity in the Italian macro-regions between 2004 and 2021. The value of the low work intensity between 2004 and 2021 had a controversial trend in the Italian macro-regions. There are macro-regions in which the value of low work intensity has decreased while in others it has

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increased. This contrast highlights a real fracture and contrast between the economy of the central-northern regions and the southern economy. The macro-regions that have experienced a reduction in the value of low work intensity are the North with -23.38%, the North-West with -24.10, the North-East with -22.06%, the Center with -4.90%. However, there are also macro-regions in which the value of low work intensity has grown such as the South with 10.16%, the South with 11.67%, the Islands with 8.42%. The level of low work intensity in the southern regions is therefore very high compared to the other Italian macro-regions. In fact, the level of low work intensity in Southern Italy is equal to 3.49 times the corresponding value in the North, 3.27 times in the North-West, 3.89 in the North-East and 2.12 in Central Italy.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we propose a clustering with a k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Two clusters are identified:

- Cluster 1: Lombardy, Marche, Veneto, Emilia Romagna, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Tuscany, Piedmont, Trentino Alto Adige, Umbria, Valle d'Aosta, Abruzzo, Liguria, Lazio, Molise;
- Cluster 2: Campania, Sicily, Sardinia, Calabria, Puglia, Basilicata.

Considering the value of the average of the clusters we can notice the following ordering: $C2 > C1$. The result is a clear contrast between the southern regions which have high levels of low work intensity and which constitute cluster 2 and the regions of Cluster 1 which instead have reduced levels of low work intensity. However we can note that Abruzzo and Molise are the only southern regions to participate in cluster 1.

Conclusions. We can note that on average the value of low work intensity remained constant in the Italian regions between 2004 and 2021. In fact, the average value of low work intensity in 2004 was equal to a value of 11.09 units and in 2021 equal to 11.05 units. Between 2004 and 2021, there were fluctuations: the minimum value was reached in 2010 with a value of 9 units while the maximum value was reached in 2012 with 12.38. However, the relevant data for the low work intensity is the enormous gap existing between the southern regions and the northern regions. Furthermore, if on the one hand in the central-northern macro-regions the value of low work intensity has decreased, on the other hand in the southern regions the same value has increased, resulting in a significant worsening of the condition of the southern population compared to the northern population. The data highlight the need to intervene with economic labour policies that are capable of increasing the demand for labour in the southern regions.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

■ Piemonte ■ Valle d'Aosta ■ Liguria ■ Lombardia ■ Trentino-Alto Adige ■ Veneto ■ Friuli-Venezia Giulia ■ Emilia-Romagna
■ Toscana ■ Umbria ■ Marche ■ Lazio ■ Abruzzo ■ Molise ■ Campania ■ Puglia ■ Basilicata ■ Calabria ■ Sicilia
■ Sardegna

